

The strong anti-tumor effect of Smp24 in lung Adenocarcinoma A549 Cells depends on its inductions of mitochondrial dysfunctions and ROS accumulation

Figure S1. Internalization of Smp24 into A549 cells. (A) The internalization of FITC-labeled Smp24 into A549 cells after 6 h of treatment. (B-E) Effect of heparan sulfate, NaN_3 , NH_4Cl and temperature on the intracellular uptake of FITC-labeled Smp24 for 6 h, respectively. The values are presented as mean \pm SEM ($n = 3$). * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, and *** $p < 0.001$ are considered statistically significant while compared with the control group.